

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 2, No. 12; December 28, 1996

Dear Readers:

This issue with four contributions is a fitting conclusion for volume 2 of an electronic journal distributed over WWW: after all, all papers deal with some aspects of the Web. Note that the one article by Paul De Bra is an award winner from the first WebNet conference (Oct.96), while the other two papers by David Marshall, Stephen Hurley and Samuel A. Rebelsky received a top paper award a few months earlier at the ED-MEDIA meeting (June 96). The permission to publish extended versions has been granted to J.UCS by AACE, the Association for Advancement of Computers in Education. For details concerning this organisation and the conferences mentioned see <http://www.aace.org>.

Hope you will enjoy reading this issue of J.UCS!

Note that for a long time J.UCS has offered the possibility to add annotations to papers that have appeared some time ago. This feature has not been used extensively, but it really should be: if in an old contribution you find something to comment on, do send this comment to jucs@iicm.edu - thus, the paper can be annotated much in the same way as the one in J.UCS Vol.2, No.4. Look at http://www.iicm.edu/jucs_2_4 to see what I mean!

Thank you for your support of J.UCS, be it as editor, author or reader, and please continue to contribute to this journal.

With best wishes for the holiday season and for 1997,

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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